

ISOLATION OF CARDIOTOXIN FROM COBRA VENOM (*NAJA TRIPUDIANS*, MONOCELLATE VARIETY)

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Isolation of an active principle "Cardiotoxin" from cobra venom (*Naja tripudians*) has been made by fractional precipitation method using different electrolytes such as Na_2SO_4 , NaCl as precipitants and it has been found to be, weight by weight, 15 times more toxic, when compared biologically, than crude cobra venom. The isoelectric point and nature of its charge at different pH values have been determined by the micro-cathphoretic and transport methods, and they agree fairly well.

During the last fifty years considerable amount of work has been done on the physiological properties of snake venoms, in particular of cobra venom. The different properties of cobra venom such as haemolysis of blood, failure of respiration and circulation etc., have been attributed to the different active constituents present in it; the more important ones isolated so far are, haemolysin (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1944, 4, 45), neurotoxin (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1941, 29, 2) and choline-esterase (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1944, 4, 78). It has been recently suggested by Sarkar *et al.* (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1942, 30, 453) that cobra venom possibly contains some other substance which brings about the stoppage of the heart. It was later on confirmed by the author (unpublished work). Cobra venom therefore contains, besides haemolysin, two other toxic principles. The one responsible for the failure of respiration has been termed as "respiratory toxin" and the other responsible for the cardiac failure has been called "cardiotoxin". An attempt has been made to isolate this active principle called "cardiotoxin" from cobra venom (*Naja tripudians*) in a pure and concentrated form. The method, as developed for its isolation, is described in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Cardiotoxin from Cobra Venom (Naja tripudians Monocellate Variety)

To a 1% solution of cobra venom* adjusted at pH 6.5 (2 g. of cobra venom dissolved in 200 c. c. of distilled water), 44g. of anhydrous sodium sulphate were gradually added with stirring. The whole mixture was kept at 37° for about 30 minutes. The precipitate was filtered off under suction (Whatman filter paper No. 50). The residue was again dissolved in water (pH 6.5) and the process repeated as before three times. The precipitate, thus obtained, was dissolved in normal saline

*The venom was extracted from the poison glands of cobra (*Naja tripudians*) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

(100 c. c.). The p_H of the solution was brought down to 2.8 and was treated with 17g. of sodium chloride. It was kept at 37° for 30 minutes and filtered. This procedure was repeated once more and the material obtained at this stage was again dissolved in 50 c. c. of normal saline. This solution (p_H adjusted to 4.2) was further treated with 12 g. of sodium chloride. It was kept at 37° for 30 minutes and filtered. The precipitate obtained was next dissolved in 50 c. c. of redistilled water (p_H adjusted to 6.0) and the cardiac principle was precipitated by 15 g. of sodium chloride. The solution was kept at 37° for 30 minutes and then filtered. The precipitate obtained at this stage contained not only the active principle but also certain amount of electrolytes, which were removed by dialysis.

Preparation of Salt-free Cardiotoxin.—A sheet of cellophane paper, free from pin holes, was tied around a large one-holed cork through which passed a funnel. The cellophane bag with its contents (a solution of cardiotoxin) was suspended in a large beaker of water and the whole arrangement was placed inside a refrigerator maintained at 7° to 8°. The surrounding water was frequently changed to remove the electrolytes which diffused out. The presence of any salt in the surrounding medium was tested from time to time until it was free from any foreign ion. The protein solution was then withdrawn and any undissolved substance was removed by centrifuging. From the clear solution cardiotoxin was precipitated with ethyl alcohol at 0°. The precipitate thus obtained was then centrifuged and repeatedly washed with ice-cold ether. It was then dried over fused calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator.

This method yielded cardiotoxin, which, weight for weight, was found to be 15 times more toxic than the crude venom, as measured biologically in terms of 'frog unit' * or 'cat unit' **

Estimation of Cardiac Activity.—The cardiac activity of the cardiotoxin obtained during and after the final stage of purification was measured by *(i) excised toad's heart method and **(ii) intravenous cat method.

Estimation of Toxicity.—To estimate the toxicity of cobra venom or cardiotoxin, pigeons weighing between 300 g. and 310 g. were used. Graded amounts of venom solution or solution of cardiotoxin were administered intramuscularly into the pigeons, and the time required for death was noted against each case. The amount of cobra venom which was just sufficient to bring about death of the animal within 6 hours of injection was taken as the 'toxic unit', and the percentage of toxicity of the unknown sample of cardiotoxin was then determined from (i) the amount required to effect death of the pigeon within that period of time and (ii) the amount of cardiotoxin obtained from a known quantity of venom.

*A 'frog unit' is used here to mean the minimum concentration of the crude venom or cardiotoxin required to bring about a stoppage of perfused toad heart (5 c. c. perfusate being used in each experiment).

**A 'cat unit' is similarly another arbitrary unit of potency which indicates that amount of crude venom or cardiotoxin (in mg./kg. body weight of cat) which will bring about an arrest of the heart beat on intravenous administration into an anaesthetised cat.

Estimation of Protein.—Percentage of protein in cobra venom or cardiotoxin was determined by the well known micro-Kjeldahl method.

The non-protein nitrogen (N. P. N.) was determined in the supernatant liquid by the above method after the complete precipitation of the protein by adding equal volumes of a 10% solution of sodium tungstate and 2/3 *N*-sulphuric acid. The difference between the total nitrogen (T. N.) and the non-protein nitrogen (N. P. N.) multiplied by the factor 0.2 gave the nitrogen content of the substance and this when further multiplied by a factor 6.25 gave the amount of the protein present in the material.

Estimation of Haemolysin.—The amount of haemolysin present in crude venom or cardiotoxin was determined according to the method developed by Slotta *et al.* (*Mem. Inst. Butantan*, 1937, 133).

TABLE I

Relative percentages of toxicity, protein and haemolysin associated with the cardiotoxin obtained at the different stages of its isolation from cobra venom (Naja tripudians, monocellate variety).

No.	Precipitate, how obtained.	Toxicity.	Protein.	Haemolysin.	Cardiotoxin.
1.	Crude venom	100 (actual protein content 90.6)	100.0	100	100
2.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the venom and precipitating at pH 6.5 with 23% Na ₂ SO ₄	40.2	41.5	75	105
3.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the ppt. (2) and precipitating at pH 6.5 with 22% Na ₂ S(O) ₄	21.5	32.0	50.8	110
4.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving ppt. (3) and precipitating at pH 6.5 with 23% Na ₂ SO ₄	9.46	21.65	20.2	75
5.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the precipitate (4) and precipitating at pH 2.8 with 17% NaCl	5.4	9.26	14.7	60
6.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the ppt. (5) and precipitating at pH 2.8 with 17% NaCl	3.45	5.21	9.82	64
7.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the ppt. (6) and precipitating at pH 4.2 with 24% NaCl	1.85	3.27	5.46	5
8.	Ppt. obtained by dissolving the ppt. (7) and precipitating at pH 6.0 with 30% NaCl.	< 0.2	2.42	< 1.0	10

Isolation of Cardiotoxin from Cobra Venom
(*Naja tripudians Binocellate Variety*)

The above method was also employed to separate the cardiotoxin from the other constituents of venom extracted from the binocellate variety of *Naja tripudians*. By adopting the above procedure, 72 mg. of cardiotoxin were obtained from 3 g. of cobra venom (binocellate variety), and its activity was found to be equivalent to 1.2 g. of cobra venom. Therefore weight for weight this purified cardiotoxin is also 15 times more toxic than the venom.

A comparative study of purification of cardiotoxin from different venoms has been made. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Substance.	Relative percentage of		Purity.
	Protein.	Activity.	
<i>Naja tripudians</i> venom (monocellate variety)	90.6	100	—
<i>Naja tripudians</i> venom (binocellate variety)	90.2	100	—
Cardiotoxin isolated from monocellate variety	2.42	40.0	15
Cardiotoxin isolated from binocellate variety	2.44	40.2	14.8

Determination of the Isoelectric Point of Cardiotoxin

Of the different properties which characterise a protein, the isoelectric point is of fundamental importance. Perrin and Hardy (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1900, 33, 385; *J. Physiol.*, 1905, 33, 351) have observed that proteins behave as ions and migrate either to the anode or to the cathode in a solution when subjected to an electrical field according to the nature of the electrical charge they carry.

The isoelectric point of proteins (the condition of no migration) is said to be the condition of minimum properties such as (i) minimum charge, (ii) minimum viscosity, (iii) minimum conductivity, (iv) minimum osmotic pressure, (v) minimum hydration, etc. and a determination of the isoelectric point is possible from a comparative study of any one of the properties mentioned above, provided it is suitable for the protein in question.

Buffer index method can also be used to determine the isoelectric point of a protein. The essence of the method is to dissolve the protein in buffers, having different pH values; the point at which the shift of pH will be the minimum is considered as the isoelectric point of the protein concerned.

Isoelectric point of a protein can also be determined by micro-cataphoretic and moving boundary methods. The microscopic method is only suitable for larger particles which are visible under the microscope or ultra-microscope, while the moving boundary method can be conveniently used for substances in the dissolved state and as such can be employed in the study of protein solutions.

It is known that when a protein solution is shaken with quartz particles, the particles acquire the charge identical with that of the protein molecule. Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1923, 6, 105) showed that the isoelectric point of gelatine or of egg-albumin, measured either in solution or adsorbed on the surface of quartz particles, gave fairly concordant results Moyer (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 122, 641) showed that the electric mobility of horse serum (pseudoglobulin) adsorbed on collodion particles was the same as the electric mobility of the protein in the dissolved state. The isoelectric point of serum albumin as determined by Abramson (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1932, 15, 575) by microcataphoretic method compares favourably well with that of Tiselius (*Nova. acta. reg. Soc. Sci. upsala'ensis*, 1933, 7, No. 4) who determined the isoelectric point of the same substance by the moving boundary method.

The nature of the electric charge and migration of the particles of cardiotoxin at different pH values have been investigated by the microcataphoretic as well as by the transport method. The experimental procedure is as follows.

Microcataphoretic Method.—Electric mobility of microscopically visible quartz particles, covered with a film of adsorbed cardiotoxin, was determined in modified Northrop-Kunitz micro-electrophoresis cells (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1925, 8, 729). In general the same concentration of cardiotoxin was used in all experiments with quartz particles. Quartz particles (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1929, 12, 169) were washed for days with distilled water after cleaning with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Approximately the same number of quartz particles of the same average size was used throughout. The quartz particles were added to the cardiotoxin solution and they were allowed to remain in contact with the solution for several minutes. Cardiotoxin solutions were made in phosphate and borate buffers between the pH 6.0 and 7.5 and pH 8.0 and 9.5 respectively. The specific resistance of each such solution was measured by using a Hartman-Braun Roller conductivity bridge in conjunction with an L & N Curtis coil resistance set, the alternating current being derived by means of a Vreeland oscillator. The potential gradient was calculated with the help of Ohm's law. The pH of the solution was determined by indicator and E. M. F. methods.

TABLE III

Cataphoretic velocities of cardiotoxin

pH .	C.V.	pH .	C.V.
6.0	+0.876	8.0	+0.25
6.5	+0.700	8.5	-0.125
7.0	+0.450	9.0	-0.360
7.5	+0.266	9.5	-0.525

Transport Method.—The apparatus consists of a U-tube, each limb of which is provided with a stop-cock exactly at the same height. Into the bottom of the U-tube, is sealed a narrow delivery tube provided with a stop-cock and

a funnel at its extremity. This tube is bent round, so as to run up behind the limbs and to bring the funnel to the same height as the top of the U-tube.

A 0.5% solution of cardiotoxin in Ringer, adjusted at different pH values was used in these experiments. The U-tube was partially filled with the same solvent in which cardiotoxin was dissolved. The stop-cocks in the two side limbs were kept open and two platinised platinum electrodes were introduced into these limbs so that they remained above the level of the stop-cocks. The cardiotoxin solution was then poured into the funnel at the extremity of the delivery tube with the stop-cock closed and the whole apparatus was then placed inside a thermostat adjusted at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1$.

The solution from the funnel was now allowed to flow slowly into the U-tube by partially opening the stop-cock in the delivery tube till the cardiotoxin solution reached the stop-cocks in the limbs of the U-tube. This required about 15 to 20 minutes times in the course of which the solution inside the U-tube acquired the temperature of the thermostat (35°). The stop-cocks in the side tubes were then closed and volumes of the solvent were then poured into the side tubes. The stop-cocks were then opened, and the electrical connection was made and the current allowed to pass for a definite period of time, at the expiry of which the stop-cocks in the limbs of the U-tube closed and the protein solution, which migrated, was taken out for quantitative measurement of the cardiac activity.

TABLE IV

Electrophoresis of cardiotoxin solution in a U-tube.

pH	Units of cardiotoxin at the	
	anode.	cathode.
8.00	1.02 frog units	9.6 frog units
8.10	<1	4.28
8.15	<1	1.64
8.20	Do	<1
8.25	1.25	Do
8.30	2.56	Do

The value of the isoelectric point of cardiotoxin as determined by these methods agree fairly well and is in the neighbourhood of pH 8.2.

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